

Prospective chromium, iron and copper sensitivity towards aromatic amino acids

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Abstract : The present article focuses on the prospective interaction of the three aromatic amino acids tyrosine (tyr), tryptophan (trp) and phenylalanine (phe) with some first row transition series members. The study reveals possibility of interaction of Cr^{VI} and Fe^{III} with all the three amino acids and of Cu^{II} with phe alone at low concentrations. The results of interactions were interpreted in the light of spectral and electrochemical evidences. The absorbance and fluorescence spectral data were found to be in agreement with those of cyclic voltammetry. Excess concentrations of both the amino acids and/or the metal ions in physiological conditions have documented harmful effects. The observed complexation may bring about a resultant decreases in the effective concentration of the aromatic acids or the metal ions or even both the entities taking part in complexation in a synergistic way.

Keywords : Tyrosine, tryptophan, phenylalanine, cyclic voltammetry, fluorescence.

Introduction

The aromatic amino acids, phenylalanine, tryptophan (essential) and tyrosine (semiessential) take part in many important biochemical processes in living organisms. Particularly in humans they play selective roles to regulate neurotransmission, appetite and as intermediates in different biochemical processes¹. These amino acids are also inherently responsible for the fluorescence property in proteins²⁻⁴. Changes in structural conformation of proteins due to metal ion complexation or any other reason is often discussed with reference to their fluorescence property^{5,6}. A direct change in the structural aspects of these amino acids due to metal ion complexation may thus be explained using their fluorescence spectral properties. In addition to their deficiency in the body, generation or uptake of excess of these amino acids is also harmful in causing different ailments like phenylketonuria, manic depression and even carcinoid syndrome. There are treatments which suggest a diet deficient in these amino acids to reduce their levels in blood plasma. In case of a liver disease three of these amino acid levels rise equally as well and cause brain damage. Metal ion complexation with bismuth was suggested as a possible remediation to

reduce the concentration of the amino acids in the blood plasma¹. However, certain concentrations of some transition elements already present in the blood plasma might play essential roles in complexation of these amino acids *in vivo*. For example iron is administered to some patients orally as ferric hydroxide and is absorbed easily in presence of ascorbic acid which reduces the ferric to ferrous form⁷. The excess ferric may be available for interactions with the amino acids under consideration.

A certain concentration of free copper is present in the blood serum which is often cited as the copper index or non-ceruloplasmin-bound copper. The required calculation is based on the total serum copper concentration less the product of the serum ceruloplasmin concentration and a factor correlating to the amount of copper bound per milligram of ceruloplasmin. A reference interval for the index is routinely identified as less than 10 µg/dL (1.6 µmol/L)⁸. Excess copper is considered neurotoxic however it may be removed by chelation using biomolecules like amino acids. In such a case the complexation may prove synergistic for removing both the excess of the amino acid and the metal ion in collaboration with one another.

Chromium is one of the most common elements in the earth's crust and exists in our environment in several oxidation states, principally as metallic Cr^0 , trivalent (+3), and hexavalent (+6) chromium. Cr^{VI} is synthesized by the oxidation of the more common and naturally occurring trivalent chromium and is highly toxic. Trivalent chromium, found in most foods and nutrient supplements, is an essential nutrient with very low toxicity. The interest in chromium as a nutritional enhancement to glucose metabolism dates back to the 1950s, when it was suggested that brewer's yeast contained trivalent chromium that could substantially lower plasma glucose levels in diabetic mice^{9,10}. More recent studies have suggested that chromium may function as a part of the oligopeptide low-molecular weight chromium-binding substance (MW 1,500 Da), which is composed of the amino acids, glycine, cysteine, glutamic acid and aspartic acid¹¹. Cationic chromium may therefore be made available in the serum for complexation by amino acids.

The present article deals with the possibility of complexation of the aromatic amino acids, tyrosine, tryptophan and phenylalanine with some first row transition metal ions. The complexation has been confirmed using spectroscopic parameters like absorbance and fluorescence. The results have been further strengthened by cyclic voltammetry.

Results and discussion

The UV-Visible spectrum of tyrosine solution in presence of first row transition metal ions reveal that absorbance at 274 nm increases pronouncedly in presence of Fe^{III} and Cr^{VI} (Fig. 1). This is probably due to higher charge densities on these metal ions compared to others. For tryptophan the trend is almost similar at the UV absorption maximum of 279 nm (Fig. 2). There is a large jump in UV absorbance for phenylalanine at 258 nm in presence of Cr^{VI} , Fe^{III} and Cu^{II} ions, the other members of the same transition series being noncomplexing with phe (Fig. 3). The results indicate that all the three aromatic amino acids are highly sensitive towards Cr^{VI} and Fe^{III} species, with phe having the highest sensitivity and an additional complexation is observed with Cu^{II} . Considering these results, binding constants of these three metal ions with the amino acids were calculated using the

Fig. 1. Absorption spectral evidences of tyrosine-metal interactions.

Fig. 2. Absorption spectral evidences of tryptophan-metal interactions.

Fig. 3. Absorption spectral evidences of phenylalanine-metal interactions.

Benesi-Hildebrand (BH) equations involving the absorbance data of the complexes.

$$1/(A - A_0) = 1/(A_1 - A_0) + 1/(A_1 - A_0)K[M] \quad (1)$$

$$Y = A + BX \quad (2)$$

where A is the absorbance of the experimental solution containing metal and amino acid, A_0 is the absorbance of the amino acid only, A_1 is the absorbance when amino acid is completely bound with the metal, $[M]$ is the metal ion concentration and K is the binding/association constant.

Eq. (1) can be presented in the simple format of eq. (2). A plot of $1/(A - A_0)$ vs $1/[M]$ appears to be a straight line and the intercept/slope of the line reveals the corresponding binding constant. The free energy change (ΔG) for the process was also calculated at temperature (T) = 298 K using the equation

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln K \quad (3)$$

The BH plot of tyr-Cr^{VI} (Fig. 4) indicate a 1 : 2 complexation. The BH plot for 1 : 1 is not supported due to the loss of its linearity. A similar inference is drawn in favor of a 1 : 2 complexation of tyr-Fe^{III} (Fig. 4) nullifying the possibility of 1 : 1 complexation as the BH plot indicates a negative intercept. BH plots for tyr-Cu^{II} complex could

Fig. 4. BH-plot of tyr-Cr⁶⁺ and tyr-Fe³⁺.

not be drawn because of insignificant changes in the absorbance with increasing metal ion concentration. Complexation of tryptophan with Cr^{VI} and Fe^{III} follows the same trend of 1 : 2 complexation of trp-Cr^{VI} and trp-Fe^{III} nullifying their 1 : 1 complexation due to similar reasons as indicated by Fig. 5. Tryptophan was also found to be

Fig. 5. BH-plot of trp-Cr⁶⁺ and trp-Fe³⁺.

insensitive towards Cu^{II} hence their BH plot could not be obtained. In accordance with Fig. 3, attractive BH plots for 1 : 1 complexes of phe with Cr^{VI}, Fe^{III} and Cu^{II} were obtained (Fig. 6). The reason behind 1 : 2 and 1 : 1 complexations can be understood on the basis of their binding constant and free energy change values. The bind-

Fig. 6. BH-plot of phe-Cr⁶⁺, phe-Fe³⁺ and phe-Cu²⁺.

ing constants for the 1 : 2 complexes are of higher order (10^6) than those of the 1 : 1 complexes of phenylalanine (10^3). The ΔG values of -37.38 kJ/mole for tyr-Cr⁶⁺ and tyr-Fe³⁺, -36 kJ/mole for trp-Cr⁶⁺ and trp-Fe³⁺ and -20 kJ/mole for phe-Cr⁶⁺, phe-Fe³⁺ and phe-Cu²⁺ also indicate more negative values for the 1 : 2 complexes of tyrosine and tryptophan than the 1 : 1 complexes of phenylalanine.

The aromatic amino acids have considerable fluorescence emission intensities which get altered upon complexation with metal ions. The steady state and excited state fluorescence spectra of tyr, trp and phe-metal complexes are shown in Figs. 7–9. The F_0/F values (where F_0 and F are the steady state fluorescence intensity in absence and in presence of the quencher) show consider-

able change with the quencher concentration. On the other hand the ratio of lifetimes τ_0/τ (without and with quencher ions) does not vary with increasing quencher concentration. The fluorescence life times of tyrosine (2.92 ns), tryptophan (2.58 ns) and phenylalanine (2.96 ns) remain practically unaltered with addition of metal ions under consideration. This suggests that the quenching of amino acid fluorescence with addition of metal ion is not dynamic or collisional quenching¹².

Rather this strongly supports the complexation between the aromatic amino acids and the metal ions in study. The F_0/F plot with increasing metal ion concentration has an exponential fit with $y = me^x$ due to its curvature and signifies the presence of both static and collisional quenching. The value of x (rate of quenching with increasing metal ion concentration) for tyrosine decreases as Fe^{3+} (7.89) > Cr^{6+} (6.35) > Cu^{2+} (2.93), which indicates a decrease in the trend of complexation (Fig. 7) with these metal ions. For tryptophan the trend goes as Cr^{6+} (8.27) > Fe^{3+} (5.39) > Cu^{2+} (2.24) indicating the least possibility of complexation with copper again (Fig. 8). The nature of F_0/F plot for phenylalanine is a straight line and signifies only static quenching in presence of metal ions. The Stern-Volmer constants may therefore be calculated for these complexes from the equation $F_0/F = 1 + K_{SV}[M]$. The K_{SV} values were found to be 13.10, 6.17 and 8.17 for Cr^{6+} , Fe^{3+} and Cu^{2+} respectively for complexation with phenylalanine (Fig. 9). Thus it is evident that only phenylalanine shows a better complexation tendency with Cu^{2+} amongst all the three aromatic amino acids.

The cyclic voltammograms provide stronger evidences of complexation as each metal in free state exhibits reversible redox mechanism in having a difference of not more than 0.06 V in the oxidation and reduction potentials¹. Upon complexation, the minimum difference in oxidation and reduction potentials become higher than 0.06 V and thus become irreversible and supports the existence of metal amino acid complex in the solution. The voltammogram of Cr^{6+} indicates a difference of 0.06 V indicating the reversibility of the ions in aqueous buffer medium. This reversibility is lost in presence of all the three amino acids in study as the differences are 0.088 V,

Fig. 7. Stern-Volmer-plot of tyr- Cr^{6+} , tyr- Fe^{3+} and tyr- Cu^{2+} .

Fig. 8. Stern-Volmer-plot of trp- Cr^{6+} , trp- Fe^{3+} and trp- Cu^{2+} .

Fig. 9. Stern-Volmer-plot of phe- Cr^{6+} , phe- Fe^{3+} and phe- Cu^{2+} .

Fig. 10. Cyclic voltammogram of Cr^{VI} and its complexes.

0.089 V and 0.075 V for tyr, trp or phe respectively confirming complexation in all the three cases (Fig. 10). Fe³⁺ ions in acetate buffer medium have 0.03 V difference in the redox potentials and represents a reversible cyclic voltammogram. Upon addition of tyr, trp or phe the values become 0.151 V, 0.099 V and 0.309 V respectively which supports complexation (Fig. 11). Cu²⁺ shows a difference of 0.06 V having reversible redox behavior. Unlike the earlier two cases Cu²⁺ does not form complex with tyr and trp which is evident from their difference in the values of redox potential (0.038 V and 0.049 V respectively) which are much less than 0.06 V indicating reversibility and hence the possibility of complexation is nullified. These results are also supported by the absorbance and fluorescence spectral data. Phe however forms complex with Cu²⁺ as can be seen from the high difference in redox potential (0.557 V) (Fig. 12) and also supported by the spectral evidence.

Fig. 11. Cyclic voltammogram of Fe^{III} and its complexes.

Fig. 12. Cyclic voltammogram of Cu^{II} and its complexes.

Experimental

Materials : The amino acids tyrosine (E. Merck), tryptophan and L-phenylalanine (Sisco Research Laboratories) were used as obtained. The FeCl₃, CrCl₃.6H₂O, K₂Cr₂O₇, NiSO₄.7H₂O, ZnSO₄.7H₂O, MnSO₄.H₂O, CoCl₂.6H₂O, CuSO₄.5H₂O salts were of analytical grade. All other chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Apparatus : A double beam Hitachi fluorescence spectrophotometer F4500 was used for spectrofluorimetric studies; we have also used Horiba Jobin Yvon Fluorocube 01-NL and 291 nm Horiba nano LED, IBH DAS-6 decay analysis software for Time Correlated Single Photon Counting (TCSPC) Lifetime Spectroscopy. The UV-Visible spectra were obtained using an Agilent 8453 diode array spectrophotometer. A digital pH meter Systronics (type no. 335) was used to measure and adjust pH of different solutions. Cyclic voltammetric (CV) measurements were done using a Bioanalytical System EPSILON electrochemical analyzer. The measurements were carried out in aqueous medium, with a three-electrode assembly comprising of a glassy carbon disk working electrode, a platinum auxiliary electrode and an aqueous Ag/AgCl reference electrode.

Methods :

Spectral studies : The tyrosine, tryptophan and L-phenylalanine solutions (1 mmol/L each) were prepared. FeCl₃, CrCl₃.6H₂O, K₂Cr₂O₇, NiSO₄.7H₂O, ZnSO₄.7H₂O, MnSO₄.H₂O, CoCl₂.6H₂O, CuSO₄.5H₂O solutions (1 mmol/L each) were prepared in triple distilled water. To identify the possible complexation, 0.1 mL metal salts

were mixed with 1 mL amino acids and volume made upto 3 mL using suitable buffers (0.1 M acetate buffer for Fe³⁺ and 0.1 M phosphate buffer for Cr⁶⁺ and Cu²⁺). The solutions were subjected to UV-Visible and fluorimetric studies for monitoring the complexation. To optimize Cr⁶⁺, Fe³⁺, Cu²⁺ transition metal-amino acid complexes, these metal salts were mixed in varying proportions with tyrosine, tryptophan and L-phenylalanine solutions (1 mmol/L each) with suitable buffer. The solutions were subjected to UV-Visible and fluorimetric studies.

Time Correlated Single Photon Counting (TCSPC) Lifetime Spectroscopy :

Fluorescence lifetimes of tyrosine, tryptophan and L-phenylalanine - Cr⁶⁺/Fe³⁺/Cu²⁺ complexes were determined by the method of time correlated single-photon counting (TCSPC) using a nanosecond diode laser as the light source at 291 nm (for tyrosine and tryptophan) and 280 nm (for phenylalanine). The IBH DAS-6 decay analysis software was used to deconvolute the fluorescence decays.

The mean fluorescence lifetimes for the decay curves were calculated from the decay times and the relative contribution of the components using the following equation

$$\tau_{av} = \frac{\sum a_i \tau_i^2}{\sum a_i \tau_i}$$

where τ_i represents decay time of the related species, τ_{av} represents the average decay time and a_i represents the coefficient of the i -th component. Tyrosin and tryptophan (1 mmol/L each) and L-phenylalanine (10 mmol/L) solutions were mixed with different stoichiometric ratio of Cr⁶⁺, Cu²⁺ using phosphate buffer (0.1 mol/L) pH 5 and acetate buffer (0.1 mol/L) pH 5 for Fe^{III} and the average life time of the complex species were identified.

Cyclic voltammetry :

The solutions for electrochemical analysis were prepared in a phosphate buffer (0.1 mol/L) pH 5 for Cr⁶⁺ and Cu²⁺ and acetate buffer (0.1 mol/L) pH 5 for Fe^{III} with amino acids. The molar ratio was maintained at tyr : Cr⁶⁺ = 1 : 2, trp : Cr⁶⁺ = 1 : 2, phe : Cr⁶⁺ = 1 : 1, tyr : Fe³⁺ = 1 : 2, trp : Fe³⁺ = 1 : 2, phe : Fe³⁺ = 1 : 1, tyr : Cu²⁺ = 1 : 2, trp : Cu²⁺ = 1 : 2, phe : Cu²⁺ = 1 : 1. These ratios were obtained from Benesi-Hildebrand equations of the spectral studies. The results were compared with the cyclic voltammetric data of direct metal salts in respective buffer media.

Conclusion

The aromatic amino acids interact with certain members of the first transition metal series at low concentrations. Cr^{VI} and Fe^{III} show spectral and electrochemical evidences of complexation with all the aromatic amino acids. Cu^{II} shows interaction with only phe and not with the tyr and trp. The other cations studied viz. Cr³⁺, Mn²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺ and Zn²⁺ do not react with these amino acids at the present conditions and concentration range. The complexation may be made suitable for the modification of amino acids, chelation and removal of the toxic metal ion like the Cr⁶⁺ or for a synergistic reduction in effective concentration of the metal ion as well as the amino acid maintaining the required conditions. The study may find potential applications in solving physiological problems and associated removal as discussed in the introduction section.

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